

Mixed ligand chelates of some multidentate heterocycles with cobalt(II) and nickel(II) imides

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Twentyfour metal chelates of the type $[\text{Ni}(\text{Im})_2(\text{B}_1)_2]$, $\text{K}[\text{Ni}(\text{Im})_2(\text{B}_2)(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]$, $[\text{Co}(\text{Im})_2(\text{B}_1)]$ and $\text{K}_2[\text{Co}(\text{Im})_2(\text{B}_2)_2]$, where Im = deprotonated phthalimide or malonimide, B_1 = 2-aminothiazole or 2-aminobenzothiazole and HB_2 = heterocyclic Schiff bases, have been prepared. The metal is coordinated through nitrogen of deprotonated imide, nitrogen of azomethine and oxygen of deprotonated phenolic hydroxyl group of the Schiff bases. The chelates are of octahedral, tetragonal, tetrahedral and octahedral structures, respectively.

Thiazole derivatives possess various biological activities¹. Similarly, the versatility of imides is also well established², however, the reactions of malonimide with transition metals are scarcely studied. Since the activity of many enzymes depend upon the interaction of a thiazole group with a transition metal ion, it is of considerable interest to study the coordination behavior of ligands containing these versatile groups. The present communication deals with the preparation and characterization of mixed ligand chelates of cobalt(II) and nickel(II) containing imides (1a,b) as primary ligands and some of the thiazole derivatives (2a-f) as secondary ligands.

Results and discussion

The molar conductance data of the chelates of Ni^{II} in 1,4-dioxane and Co^{II} in THF show that chelates having sl. nos. 1, 2, 7, 8, 13, 14, 19, 20 (Table 1) are monomeric and non-electrolytes, sl. nos. 3-6, 9-12 are two species ions while sl. nos. 15-18, 21-24 are three species ions.

Table 1. Physical data of the chelates*

Sl no.	Compl.**	M.p °C	Mol cond. $\Omega^{-1} \text{cm}^{-1} \text{mol}^{-1}$
1.	$[\text{Ni}(\text{M})_2(\text{ATZ})_2]$	150	5
2.	$[\text{Ni}(\text{M})_2(\text{ABTZ})_2]$	158	3
3.	$\text{K}[\text{Ni}(\text{M})_2(\text{STZ}_1)(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]$	201	103
4.	$\text{K}[\text{Ni}(\text{M})_2(\text{STZ}_2)(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]$	196	98
5.	$\text{K}[\text{Ni}(\text{M})_2(\text{SBTZ}_1)(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]$	215	100
6.	$\text{K}[\text{Ni}(\text{M})_2(\text{SBTZ}_2)(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]$	218	106
7.	$[\text{Ni}(\text{P})_2(\text{ATZ})_2]$	162	2
8.	$[\text{Ni}(\text{P})_2(\text{ABTZ})_2]$	170	4
9.	$\text{K}[\text{Ni}(\text{P})_2(\text{STZ}_1)(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]$	200	99
10.	$\text{K}[\text{Ni}(\text{P})_2(\text{STZ}_2)(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]$	209	95
11.	$\text{K}[\text{Ni}(\text{P})_2(\text{SBTZ}_1)(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]$	196	90
12.	$\text{K}[\text{Ni}(\text{P})_2(\text{SBTZ}_2)(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]$	211	98
13.	$[\text{Co}(\text{M})_2(\text{ATZ})]$	168	1
14.	$[\text{Co}(\text{M})_2(\text{ABTZ})]$	170	2
15.	$\text{K}_2[\text{Co}(\text{M})_2(\text{STZ}_1)_2]$	195	188
16.	$\text{K}_2[\text{Co}(\text{M})_2(\text{STZ}_2)_2]$	220	175
17.	$\text{K}_2[\text{Co}(\text{M})_2(\text{SBTZ}_1)_2]$	230	190
18.	$\text{K}_2[\text{Co}(\text{M})_2(\text{SBTZ}_2)_2]$	212	192
19.	$[\text{Co}(\text{P})_2(\text{ATZ})]$	188	3
20.	$[\text{Co}(\text{P})_2(\text{ABTZ})]$	170	10
21.	$\text{K}_2[\text{Co}(\text{P})_2(\text{STZ}_1)_2]$	212	177
22.	$\text{K}_2[\text{Co}(\text{P})_2(\text{STZ}_2)_2]$	201	182
23.	$\text{K}_2[\text{Co}(\text{P})_2(\text{SBTZ}_1)_2]$	220	185
24.	$\text{K}_2[\text{Co}(\text{P})_2(\text{SBTZ}_2)_2]$	230	180

*All compounds gave satisfactory C, H, N and metal analyses.

**MH = Malonimide, PH = phthalimide, ATZ = 2-aminothiazole, ABTZ = 2-aminobenzothiazole, STZ_1 = (2-hydroxy-1-benzaldehyde)-2-aminothiazole, STZ_2 = (2-hydroxy-1-naphthaldehyde)-2-aminothiazole, SBTZ_1 = (2-hydroxy-1-benzaldehyde)-2-amino-4-phenyl-5-phenylazothiazole, SBTZ_2 = (2-hydroxy-1-naphthaldehyde)-2-amino-4-phenyl-5-phenylazothiazole.

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In the infrared spectra of the chelates, the lower shifts of ν_{CO} from 1730 to $\approx 1700 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ in the phthalimide series, from 1680 to 1650 cm^{-1} in the malonimide series and upward shift of ν_{CN} from 1480 to 1500 cm^{-1} in both the series could be attributed to coordination of imide ion through nitrogen³. In the IR spectra of ATZ or ABTZ, the bands at $3400 (\nu_{\text{sym}} \text{NH}_2 + \nu_{\text{asym}} \text{NH}_2)$, $1600 (\text{NH}_2)$ and 780 cm^{-1} (CS) suffered lower shifts of ≈ 80 , ≈ 25 and $15\text{--}20 \text{ cm}^{-1}$, respectively, indicating coordination of the amino group⁴ and sulfur⁵. In case of the Schiff base, the disappearance of broad band at 2900 cm^{-1} (H-bonded phenolic OH) and upward shift ($\approx 20 \text{ cm}^{-1}$) in the ν_{CO} confirm the deprotonation and coordination of phenolic OH group⁶. The upward shifts in the 1580 and 1620 cm^{-1} bands due to central C=N and ring C=N stretch⁷ to 1610 and 1630 cm^{-1} indicate coordination of Schiff bases through azomethine group⁸. The appearance of new bands at 850 and 600 cm^{-1} in the spectra of chelates of sl. nos. 3–6, 9–12 confirms water coordination⁴.

The magnetic moments (at 296 K) of Ni^{II} chelates of sl. nos. 1, 2, 7, 8 were 3.40–3.60 B.M. while for the rest of the chelates the values were in the range 2.65–2.85 B.M. The former ones of higher than the spin-only values may be due to mixing of upper states via spin-orbit coupling⁹, while in the later cases, the lower than spin-only values indicate distortion in the octahedral geometry. The magnetic studies at cryogenic temperatures (296–77 K) showed practically no variation (3.40–3.60 to 3.20–3.43 B.M.), confirming the 'A' ground term of the Ni^{II} ion in octahedral geometry. In other cases, where the variation was more (2.65–2.88 to 2.22–2.28 B.M.), the distortion in octahedral geometry was proved. In case of the Co^{II} chelate of sl. nos. 15–18, 21–24, the magnetic moments 4.82–5.08 B.M. (296 K) suffered appreciable variation with temperature (3.33–3.11 at 77 K), which confirmed 'T' ground term of Co^{II} ion and high-spin octahedral geometry of the chelates. In the other chelates of Co^{II} ; the temperature variation of magnetic moments was negligible (4.50–4.62 B.M. at 296 K and 4.22–4.28 B.M. at 77 K) which proved 'A' ground term and tetrahedral geometry of the chelates.

The electronic spectral band positions of the Ni^{II} chelates of ATZ and ABTZ observed at $9000\text{--}9500 (\nu_1)$, $15000\text{--}16000 (\nu_2)$ and $27000\text{--}28400 \text{ cm}^{-1} (\nu_3)$ when fitted to standard energy equations¹⁰ to calculate the ligand field parameters, viz. $10 Dq$, B , β , ν_2/ν_1 , gave the values which are characteristic of Ni^{II} octahedral complexes¹¹. The spectra of other Ni^{II} chelates show features of typical Ni^{II} with tetragonal distortion. In the transformation of octahedral to tetragonal symmetry, orbitally excited triplet terms, ${}^3T_{2g}$ and ${}^3T_{1g}$, are split into ${}^3B_{2g} + {}^3E_g$ and ${}^3A_{2g} + {}^3E_g$, respectively; usually, the splitting of the ${}^3T_{2g}$ term is appreciable enough to be experimentally observed. Nevertheless, several cases have been reported where the splitting of the ${}^3T_{1g}$

(F) term occurs¹², and in a limited number of complexes, the splitting of the ${}^3T_{1g}$ (P) has been reported¹³. For the present series, pronounced tetragonal splitting for the excited levels, ${}^3T_{2g}$ (F) and ${}^3T_{1g}$ (F) have been observed. The split components for ${}^3T_{2g}$ (F) were observed near 8500 and 11000 cm^{-1} , the relative intensity of the former being higher. The components of ${}^3T_{1g}$ (F) are located near 14000 and 16000 cm^{-1} , respectively, the intensity of the latter being stronger. The two stronger components of T_{2g} and T_{1g} (F) terms are assigned to the transitions belonging to E_g levels which indicates that the tetragonal distortion to the octahedron involves the elongation along the four-fold axis. The transition energies νB_{2g} and νE_g of the ${}^3T_{2g}$ level are related to the tetragonal splitting parameters D_s and D_t and the splitting parameters for in-plane and for axial ligands, D_{qxy} and D_{qz} , respectively, by the equations:

$$D_t = 4/35 (\nu B_{2g} - \nu E_g)$$

$$D_{\text{qxy}} = 1/10 (\nu B_{2g})$$

$$D'_t = 1/10 (2\nu E_g - \nu B_{2g})$$

$$\Delta\nu [{}^3T_{1g} (F)] = 6D_s - (5/4) D_t$$

The splitting of the t_{2g} and e_g orbitals, δt_{2g} and δe_g , respectively, of the Ni^{II} ion and Mc-Clure's parameters¹⁴, δ_σ and δ_π were determined from the crystal field parameters D_s and D_t by the equations,

$$\delta t_{2g} = 3D_s - 5D_t$$

$$\delta e_g = 4D_s + 5D_t$$

$$\delta_\sigma = -(1/8) (15D_t + 12 D_s)$$

$$\delta_\pi = (1/2) (5D_t - 3D_s)$$

The results of these calculations are summarized in Table 2. The parameter D_s is found consistently higher than D_t throughout the series. The ratio D_t/D_s provides a measure for r^2/R^2 , where r is the average radius of the d -shell and R the average metal-ligands distance. The negative sign of δ_σ provides further evidence of stronger σ bonding along the xy -plane and positive value of δ_π indicates that the π bonding effect is relatively more important along the axial direction.

The electronic spectra of the Co^{II} chelates of STZ and SBTZ ligands in THF consist of two bands at $\approx 16000 (\nu_2)$ and $\approx 18300 \text{ cm}^{-1} (\nu_3)$ in the phthalimide series and at $\approx 14500 (\nu_2)$ and $17100 \text{ cm}^{-1} (\nu_3)$ in the malonimide series. These correspond to the transitions ${}^4T_{1g} (F) \rightarrow {}^4A_{2g}$ and ${}^4T_{1g} (F) \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g} (P)$, respectively¹⁵, the characteristic features of octahedral Co^{II} complexes. Other Co^{II} chelates show two bands at $\approx 14000 (\nu_1)$ and 30000 cm^{-1} , the latter being of very high intensity ($\epsilon \approx 8000 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ cm}^{-1} \text{ mol}^{-1}$), which proves it to be a $L \rightarrow M$ charge transfer band of cobalt(II) tetrahedral chelates.

Table 2 Calculated spectral parameters (cm⁻¹) for the Ni^{II} tetragonal chelates

Sl no	D _t	D _q ^{xy}	D _q ^z	D _s	δ _{ee}	δ _{2g}	δ _σ	δ _π
3	343	1200	600	405	3335	-500	-1250	+250
4	343	1180	580	472	3603	-299	-1351	+150
5	331	1140	560	486	3599	197	-1350	+099
6	297	1100	580	479	3401	-048	-1275	+024
9	343	1200	600	405	3335	-500	-1250	+250
10	343	1190	590	522	3803	149	-1426	+075
11	297	1120	600	429	3201	-198	-1200	+099
12	320	1100	540	500	3600	-100	-1350	+050

*Same as in Table 1

Thermal studies indicate that in case of chelates of sl nos 3–6, 9–12, a weight loss equivalent to two water molecules was observed in TG measurements at around 175° indicating the presence of these water molecules as coordinated water¹⁶. The endothermic peak in the DTA in the region 170–185° in these cases confirms this conclusion.

Experimental

The thermal studies were done for powdered samples on a Rigaku 8150 instrument at a heating rate of 5°/min in an atmosphere of air. Other physical methods were the same as reported earlier¹⁷.

Phthalimide was obtained from Fluka. All other chemicals were of A.R. grade (B.D.H., E. Merck or Glaxo) and used as received. The solvents were distilled twice before use.

The heterocyclic Schiff bases were synthesized as reported earlier⁴.

Malonimide To malonic acid (180 g) was added slowly with cooling and shaking concentrated ammonia solution (140 ml). The reaction mixture was heated when water distilled first at 100° followed by evolution of ammonia, the temperature first dropped slightly and then rose to 165°. Malonimide was collected in absolute alcohol. It was then crystallized by slow evaporation of alcohol.

Metal(II) imides The aqueous solution of metal salt [cobalt(II) chloride dihydrate and nickel(II) sulfate heptahydrate] and potassium imide were mixed in 1:2 molar ratio. The green and blue solids formed in the case of Ni^{II} and Co^{II}, respectively, were washed with distilled water and dried in an oven at 70°. Analytical data were in accordance with the formula [Ni(Im)₂(H₂O)₄] and [Co(Im)₂(H₂O)₂] where Im = deprotonated imide molecule.

Mixed ligand complexes A mixture of the methanolic solution of the above complexes and the thiazole derivatives (1:1 molar ratio, 0.05 M, 50 ml each) was refluxed on a water bath for 0.5 h and then allowed to stand for 5–6 h. The light green and pink-violet solids formed in case of the Ni^{II} complexes (sl nos 1–12) and the Co^{II} complexes (sl nos 15–18, 21–24) respectively were washed with methanol and acetone and then dried in a desiccator over anhydrous sulfuric acid.

Chelates of Co^{II} (sl nos 13, 14, 19, 20) To a methanolic solution of cobalt(II) chloride dihydrate, methanolic solution of thiazole derivatives and alcoholic solution/suspension of the potassium salt of imide were added in a molar ratio of 1:1:2. Blue coloured chelates that separated immediately, were washed with water, methanol and ether, and then crystallized from THF as blue crystals.

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References

1. L. Henning, R. Kimmse, O. Hammenich, S. Larsen, H. Faryndahl, H. Toftlund and J. Becher, *Inorg Chim Acta* 1995, **67**, 234. B. Katri, L. Simon, R. Anne, C. Gerard, D. Francoise and M. Bernaud, *Inorg Chem* 1996, **35**, 387. H. Sigel and A. Sigel, *J Indian Chem Soc* 2000, **77**, 501.
2. *Metal Ions in Biological Systems*, eds. A. Sigel and H. Sigel, Marcel Dekker, New York, 2001, Vol. 38.
3. V. Mishra, *Acta Chim Hung* 1990, **127**, 155.
4. K. Nakamoto, *Infrared and Raman Spectra of Inorganic and Coordination Compounds*, Wiley Interscience, New York, 1978.
5. M. J. M. Campbell, R. Grzeskowiak and G. S. Juneja, *J Inorg Nucl Chem* 1978, **40**, 1247.
6. V. Mishra, Proceedings of the Annual Convention of Chemists, Indian Chemical Society, Calcutta, 1993, Abstr. no. ING(OP) 20.
7. M. R. Moahamed and M. T. El Hary, *J Inorg Nucl Chem* 1980, **42**, 349.
8. M. Consiglio, F. Maggio, T. Pizzino and V. Homano, *Inorg Nucl Chem Lett* 1976, **14**, 135.
9. H. W. Kouwenhoven, J. Lewis and R. S. Nyholm, *Proc Chem Soc* 1961, 220.
10. R. L. Carlin, *Transition Met Chem* 1965, **1**, 20.

Note

11. C. K. Jorgenson, *Acta Chim. Scand.*, 1956, **10**, 887.
12. O. Botrup and C. K. Jorgenson, *Acta Chim. Scand.*, 1957, **11**, 1223; R. L. Chiang and R. S. Drago, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1971, **10**, 453.
13. A. B. P. Lever. "Inorganic Electronic Spectroscopy," 2nd. ed., Elsevier, Amsterdam, 1984.
14. D. S. Mc Clure. "Advances in Chemistry of Coordination Compounds", ed. S. Krischner, Mc-Millan, New York, 1961, p. 498.
15. S. Buffagni, L. M. Vallarino and J. V. Quagliano, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1964, **3**, 480.
16. A. V. Nikoleav, V. A. Longvinenko and L. I. Mavachina. "Thermal Analysis", Academic, New York, 1969, Vol. 2, p. 779.
17. V. Mishra, D. K. Saksena and M. C. Jain, *Synth. React. Inorg. Metal-Org. Chem.*, 1987, **17**, 987.